

SUITABILITY OF OWOH MOULDING SAND FOR FOUNDRY INDUSTRIES USING UMULUMGBE CLAY AS BINDER

^{1*}Agbo Alfred Ogbodo, ²Nevo Cornelius Ogochukwu and ³Chukwujindu Sunday

¹Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

²Department of Chemical Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

³Department of Mechanical and Production Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

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Abstract: This research, investigated the suitability of Owoh moulding sand for foundry applications. Chemical analysis was conducted using X-ray fluorescence (XRF). Result of the chemical analysis revealed that Owoh River sand has 90.5% SiO₂, 3.9% Fe₂O₃ and 3.21% CaO as its predominant oxides. The silica content of 90.50% compares well with the acceptable values of between 80% and 97% recommended for moulding. Sieve analysis and other mechanical tests were conducted using accepted international standard. From the sieve analysis results, it was revealed that Owoh River sand has grain fineness number of 71.97. The mechanical properties test conducted were green compressive strength, green shear strength, dry compressive strength, dry shear strength, permeability and moisture content. The results obtained showed that the green compressive strength was 29.5KN/m², dry compressive strength was 225KN/m², permeability was 155.00 (No) and moisture content was 4.20% at 5% water content, and 8% Umulumgbe clay content. From the results, it was found that 5% water content and 8% Umulumgbe clay content were most suitable for moulding Owoh River sand for applications in non-ferrous foundry and therefore, the result compares favourable with the international accepted moulding standard. Therefore Umulumgbe clay content could serve as alternative to other conventional binder like bentonite in the non-ferrous foundry industries.

Keywords: Moulding, Foundry, Silica, Permeability, Umulumgbe.

1. Introduction

Moulding sand is a heat-resistant mixture of sand, clay and water used to form moulds for casting molten metal into desired shapes. Moulds prepared from sand are comparatively cheap and appropriately refractory including for steel foundries, thus over 60% of metal casting are manufactured by the sand casting processes (Rao, 2003). Foundry sand is made up of silica groups. The mineral silica is one of the major ingredients in moulding sand apart from clay and water because it imparts refractoriness, chemical resistivity, bonding strength, high hardness and permeability to the sand. It is characterized with a high melting point of about 1710⁰C – 1713⁰C (Agbo et al., 2018). The properties of good moulding sand include permeability, plasticity, refractoriness, chemical stability, cohesiveness, dry compressive strength and green compressive strength (Shuaibu-babata and Olumodeji 2014). The foundry business, which is importance to production, is strongly reliant on the quality of the sand used in moulding operations. Sand is the primary raw materials because of its unique features, such as its ability to

endure high temperatures without decomposing making it perfect for a wide range of foundry and construction applications (Abdullahi &Katsina, 2018). Foundry sands are divided into two types: ferrous foundries, which manufacture steel castings, and non-ferrous foundries, which are metals such as aluminium, copper, zinc and lead (Opeoluwad&Antonie, 2013). The applicability of the sand is mostly determined by their physical features, such as moisture content, grain size, and clay content, which may all have a considerable influence on moulding performance and, as a result, the quality of cast products. Previous research has looked at many types of natural sand deposits and their possible applications in foundry processes. Katsina et al (2013) investigated beach sands from the Ughelli, Warri and Ethiopia rivers and concluded that they were suitable for foundry applications. However, sand from the Lagos beach required sifting to remove coarse particles, highlighting the difference in sand quality even within close geographical proximity.

Metal casting is the production of shaped articles by pouring molten metal into moulds (.Beely, 2001). Metal casting has several design advantages such as size, complexity, weight, saving, production of prototypes, wide range of properties and versatility. It also has comparative advantages over all other metal forming processes such as low cost, versatility in production and dimensional accuracy depending on the type of moulding and casting process employed. Metal casting can be accomplished by either expendable mould processes or permanent mould processes (Ademoh and Abdullahi, 2009). The common method often employed is expendable moulding involving sand casting or which the use of silica sand is popular. Silica sand (SiO_2) occurs naturally in abundance. It is cheap and suitable for repeated use and can withstand high temperature. Due to the above properties, silica sand is well suited for moulding sand. Despite all these properties, pure silica sand requires clay to bond its particles together to make it suitable for moulding (Aweda and Jimoh, 2009).

Sand casting which is perhaps the most versatile of the casting methods can be used for casting components ranging in size from very small to extremely large (Ibitoye 2005).

2.0 Materials and Method

The materials used for this research work were locally sourced. The silica sand was forced from Owoh in Nkanu East Local Government Area, while the binding clay was sourced from Umulumgbe in Udi Local Government Area and Alkali-free dextrine was procured in Ogbete local market, Enugu.

Furthermore, the study's relevance stems from its ability to minimize reliance on imported resources, lower production costs, and promote the adoption of ecologically beneficial alternatives. This study contributes to the broader goal of sustainable development in the foundry sector by assessing the impact of moisture content on the foundry performance of sand from the Owoh River sand, which is consistent with global efforts to promote environmentally conscious industrial practices. According to Dieter (1966), sand casting qualities must fulfill particular specifications to assure high -quality metal grades; the chemical composition of the sand and binder was determined using X-ray fluorescence (XRF). Mechanical sieve analysis was used to measure the particle size distribution of sand, which is critical in moulding and casting quality.

Several experiments were conducted to evaluate the mechanical qualities, including green compression strength, green shear strength, dry compression strength, and dry shear strength.

These experiments gave information on the sand's performance in both damp and dry conditions during normal foundry operations. The permeability of sand was also tested to determine its capacity to enable gasses to escape during the casting process and ensure defect- free casting.

With an emphasis on managing moisture content to improve performance in sustainable casting process, the combination of chemical and mechanical test offered a thorough assessment of the sand's suitability for foundry applications.

2.1 Preparation and determination of Grain Size

Unwanted elements were initially removed from Owoh River sand by hand -picking to prepare for sustainable foundry procedures. After giving the sand a thorough cleaning, It was sieved to remove any coarse particles and was oven dried at 110°C to remove any remaining moisture sand's grain size distribution. An electrical sieving machine was used to the silica's grain size distribution. A weighing scale was used to precisely measure the dry sand before it was put on top of a series of sieve with increasing narrower holes. The amount of sand retained in each mesh was measures and noted after the sieving machine ran for 40 minutes. The American Foundry Society (AFS) grain fineness number was calculated using the following method to obtain the grain fineness number (GFN)

$$AFS \text{ grain fineness number} = \frac{\text{Product of grain size}}{\text{Amount retained(\%)}} \quad (1)$$

2.2 Determination of Green Strength

A universal sand testing equipment was used to determine the green strength of Owoh River sand. A standard test sample with dimension of 7cm in diameter and 7 cm in height was placed into the sand testing machine's compression head. The sample was place into the machine once it had been securely fastened. The sample reached its maximum strength and then failed whenthe machine applied increasing pressure. At this moment, the measuring scale's magnetic rider moved to the location that corresponded to mechanical stresses during molding procedures in foundy applications, this exact measurement of green strength is essential.

2.3 Determination of Dry Strength.

A universal sand testing equipment was used to assess the prepared Owoh River sand sample's dry compression strength (DCS). A standard sample measuring 7 cm in diameter and 7cm in height was oven dried for 15minutes at 110°C before the samples were allowed to cool at room temperature.

The sample was placed within the universal sand testing equipment, and a progressively higher stress was applied using the compression head. The samples finally featured at its maximum load - bearing capacity as the load increased. To assess the sand viability for high temperature foundry applications, at this of failure was recorded as the dry compression strength (DCS), which provides vital information on the sand's structural integrity under dry circumstances.

2.4 Determination of Dry Shear Strength

The dry shear strength of the prepared sand sample was evaluated by first drying a 7cm diameter x 7 cm height sample in an oven at 110°C for 40minutes. The samples were allowed to cool at room temperature, the samples were subjected to shear testing. The shear strength was measured at the point of failure, which provided an important indicator of the sand's resistance to shear pressures under dry circumstances. This number is significant in determining whether the sand is suitable for moulding in the foundry processes, where shear resistance is essential for mould stability.

2.5 Determination of Green Shear Strength

The green shear strength of the sand samples were determined by utilizing a process similar to the green compressive strength test with a shear head. The prepared sample was exposed to an increasing shearing force,

and the green shearing strength was measured at the point of failure. This test is critical for determining the sample's resistance to shear pressures in its green condition, which provides information about its stability and appropriateness for moulding procedures in foundry applications.

2.6 Determination of Permeability

The permeability of sand samples was determined using standard sample specimen of 7 cm in diameter and 7 cm in height. The specimen was mounted on a permeability meter, and constant pressure was applied. The pressure drop across the specimen was measured using a calibrated pressure gauge, which directly provided the permeability values and numbers. This test is essential for assessing the sand's ability to allow gases to pass through during casting, a critical factor in preventing casting defects in foundry operations.

2.7 Refractoriness

The sand was mixed with pure and alkali -free dextrin to create a homogenous slurry, the refractoriness of the sample was evaluated. The samples were shaped into a cone, this substance was oven -dried at 110°C. The cone-shaped samples were dried and then sintered at 1000°C in a furnace. A pyrometric cone with a known temperature was positioned next to the sample in the furnace to assess refractoriness. The temperature was raised gradually until the sample and the pyrometric cone reached their respective softening point. The refractoriness of the sample was measured at the temperature at which it softened. This characteristic, which shows the material's capacity to tolerate intense heat without melting, is essential for assessing the sand's appropriateness in high temperature foundry application

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this research work were presented in Tables 3.1 – 3.4 and figures 3.1 – 4.5.

Table 4.1 shows the results of sieve analysis and grain fineness number of Owoh River sand. According to the American Foundrymen's Society (AFS) (1963) and Agbo et al (2017), 40 to 330 average fineness is suitable for moulding and foundry applications. The Owoh River sand has an average fineness number of 71.97 (see Table 3.1). The grain fineness number is a useful parameter that represents the sieve number through which all the sand grain would pass through, if they were of the same sizes. From the Table 3.1, it was shown that the grain were well distributed with about 70% concentration of the sand grains been retained by the adjacent sieve size of 0.180mm, 1.125mm and 0.09mm.

Table 3.2 shows the chemical analysis of Owoh River sand. From the Table 4.2, it was shown that Owoh River sand has SiO₂ (90.50%), Fe₂O₃ (3.90%), Al₂O₃ (4.86%) and CaO (3.21%) as its predominant oxides with some trace oxides as BaO (0.042%), V₂O₅ (0.05%) and NiO (0.013%). From the table 3.2, the silica content of 90.5% compares well with the acceptable values of between 80% and 97% recommended for moulding (Jain 2008) but cannot be used for ferrous castings because according to Mclaws (1971), ideal sand for ferrous castings should contain silica in the region of 98% - 99%. It can also be seen from Table 3.26 that the percentage of SiO₂ content for Chelford, Warri and Ughellium River sand samples are close to that of Owoh River sand sample.

Moulding experiments using Umulumbe clay content with very composition of water contents were carried out to determine the basic mechanical/foundry properties such as the green compressive strength, green shear strength, dry compressive strength, dry shear strength, permeability and moisture content of the moulding properties of Owoh River sand. The green compressive strength increased with increase in moisture content reaching a maximum value of 29.60KN/m² at 5% water content. After which decreased to 29.20KN/m² at 6%

water content. Further increase in the percentage of water content above 5% water led reduction in the green compressive strength. Decrease in green compressive strength with increase water content suggest the presence of excess moisture in the sand mould.

Dry compressive strength increased with increase in moisture content. The dry compressive strength increased steadily as the water content introduced increased. The dry compressive strength increased from 182.00KN/m² at 2% waer content to 233.0KN/m² at 6% water content. The values of dry compressive strength were in agreement with the American Foundrymen’s Standard (AFS) shown in table 3.4b.

The permeability of Owoh River sand increased as the moisture content increased at maximum water content of 4% after which decreased. Further addition of water after 4% water content contributes effectively in the reduction of permeability. The increase in moisture content of Owoh River sand contributed efficiently in the reduction of permeability of Owoh River Sand.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions are drawn from the results

1. Chemical analysis results reveals that the sand contained more than 90% silica which is suitable for non-ferrous alloy casting because of is low refractoriness.
2. The sand blended with 8%Umulumgbe clay content and 5% water content was the best mixture. These properties compared favourable with the proportion of the moulding sand currently used in foundries for casting of non-ferrous alloys.
3. From the sieve analysis results it was revealed that the grain fineness number was found to be 71.97 which falls in accordance with the range of 40 to 330 average grain fineness number suitable for moulding sand.

Table 3.1 Mechanical Sieve analysis results of Owoh River sand

S/NO	Aperture sizes (mm)	Sand retained on each sieve (g)	Percentage of sand retained	Multiplier	Products
1.	1.00	12.50	1.23	9	11.07
2.	0.71	14.06	1.38	15	20.70
3.	0.50	52.40	5.16	25	129.00
4.	0.355	100.71	9.91	35	346.85
5.	0.250	65.20	6.42	45	288.90
6.	0.180	340.80	33.54	60	2012.40
7.	1.125	220.00	21.65	81	1753.65
8.	0.09	160.56	15.49	118	1827.82
9.	0.063	50	4.92	164	806.88
10.	Total	1016.17	100		7197.27

Grain fineness number = 71.97

Table 3.2: Chemical Analysis of Owoh River sand

Oxides	SiO ₂	V ₂ O ₅	MnO	Fe ₂ O ₃	NiO	CuO	Nb ₂ O ₅
Concentration (%)	90.50	0.05	1.42	3.90	0.013	0.047	0.021
Oxides	NO ₃	SO ₃	CaO	K ₂ O	BaO	Al ₂ O ₃	ZrO ₂

Concentration (%)	0.01	1.82	3.21	1.84	0.042	4.86	0.75
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Table 3.2b: Chemical Composition of some foundry sand

Constituents	Chelford	Warri River sand %	Ethiopia River Sand %	Ughelli River sand %	Lagos Barbeach sand %
SiO ₂	97.91	96.18	98.12	97.01	53.16
Al ₂ O ₃	1.13	2.76	0.91	1.96	19.40
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.50	0.06	0.16	0.13	4.70
CaO	-	-	-	-	2.66
MgO	-	-	-	-	2.08
K ₂ O	0.25	-	-	-	-
Loss on Ignition	0.21	1.00	0.72	0.90	18.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Table 3.3: Chemical Analysis of Umulumgbe clay deposit

Oxides	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	TiO ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CuO	AS ₂ O ₃
Concentration (%)	51.0	26.10	0.260	1.80	4.270	0.021	0.011
Oxides	ZrO ₂	MbO ₃	Eu ₂ O ₃	BaO	PbO	CdO	
Concentration (%)	0.270	0.026	0.11	0.04	0.04	1.82	

Table 3.4b: Satisfactory mould property ranges for sand castings

Metal	Green compressive strength (KN/m ²)	Dry strength (KN/m ²)	Permeability (No)
Heavy steel	70 – 85	1000 – 2000	130 – 300
Light steel	70 – 85	400 – 1000	125 – 200
Heavy grey iron	70 – 105	50 – 800	70 – 120
Aluminium	50 – 70	200 – 550	10 – 30
Brass and bronze	55 – 85	200 – 860	15 – 40
Light grey iron	50 – 85	200 – 550	20 – 50
Malleable iron	45 – 55	210 – 550	20 – 60
Medium grey iron	70 - 105	350 - 800	40 - 80

Table 3.4a: Moulding properties of Owoh River sand using 8% of Umulumbe clay content.

Water (%)	Green Compressive Strength	Green shear strength (KN/m ²)	Dry compressive strength (KN/m ²)	Dry shear strength (KN/m ²)	Permeability (No)	Moisture content (%)
2	25.00	6.20	182.00	55.20	154.20	2.50
3	27.80	6.35	194.11	57.10	156.10	2.90
4	28.90	7.60	210.20	59.33	156.30	3.52
5	29.50	7.78	225.00	64.00	155.00	4.20
6	29.30	7.42	233.00	66.50	153.00	4.63

Fig 3.1: The relationship between aperture size and percentage sand retained

Fig. 3.2: Effect of water content on the Green Compressive Strength of Owoh River Sand

Fig. 3.3: Effect of water content on the Dry Compressive Strength of Owoh River Sand

Fig. 3.4: Effect of water content on the Permeability of Owoh River Sand

Fig. 3.5: Effect of water content on the Moisture Content of Owoh River Sand

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